

Effectiveness of Non-Monetary Motivations on Job Performance in Tanzania: A Case of Institutions in Tabora Municipality, Tanzania

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Abstract:

This study sought to examine “the effectiveness of non-monetary motivations on job performance in public institutions; a case of Tabora Municipal Council. The study was confined to four specific objectives which were: (1) To examine the process of Recognizing workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipal Council (2) To examine the process of Promoting workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipal Council (3) To determine the process of Training workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipal Council (4) To determine the relationship between non-

monetary motivations and employees' job performance in Tabora Municipal Council. A descriptive correlational study design was adopted and a total sample of 148 respondents was consulted. The stratified and purposive sampling techniques were used to select respondents. Questionnaires were employed as tools of data collection. Quantitative data were analyzed by frequencies, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation, and the data were presented in tables and figures. The study findings revealed that the processes of non-monetary motivations follow labor and employment policy guidelines at Tabora Municipality. Furthermore, the study findings revealed that factors for successful practices are the use of fairness, policy, and evaluation feedback reports. The study findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between non-monetary motivations and job performance. Lastly, the study recommends that Trust from all employees must be taken into account to create a fair and equal chance when it comes to the awarding process. Management members should be trained properly to conduct the employee performance review as one of the tool requirements in granting non-monetary motivation awards to workers.

Keywords: *Performance, Management, Human Resources, Productivity, Employer Expectations, Evaluation, Appraisal.*

Introduction

The overall success of an organization in achieving its strategic objectives relies heavily on the motivation level of employees (Jyothi, 2016). All organizations, regardless of sector, size, or industry require a motivated workforce that

ensures the efficiency, high organizational output, and prosperity of the organization. Demotivated employees are likely to put in little or no effort in their jobs, produce low quality, work mostly avoid their workplace, and even exit the organization if provided opportunity (Mustafa &

Ali, 2019). Motivation is the most important matter for every organization public or private sector.

For the success of any organization, motivation plays an important role. All organization encounters the matter of motivation whether they are in the public or private sector (Gachengo & Wekesa, 2017). Employees who are motivated to work are likely to be determined, innovative, and competent. Motivated employees are contented, dedicated, and enthusiastic, resulting in an optimum level of employee retention, loyalty, and harmony. This contributes significantly to the growth and development of the overall organization

Globally, much has been investigated about the employee's non-monetary motivation and job performance. For instance, a study conducted by Bakar, *et al.* (2017) on non-monetary incentives to improve job performance at a Property Company in Penang Malaysia revealed that among the motivational factors, two variables were found to be significant predictors of job performance. Training contributed 40.4% to job performance while promotion contributed an additional 3% to that of training. An interesting finding of the research is that intrinsic motivational factors are considered more important compared to extrinsic motivational factors.

In India, a study by Robescu and Iancu (2016) on the effects of motivation on employee performance in organizations found that although monetary rewards can be a very powerful determinant of employee motivation and performance which, in turn, can lead to important returns in terms of firm-level performance. However, monetary rewards do not always lead to these desirable outcomes. The study further indicated that nonmonetary motivational factors are powerful in making employees perform better and even be satisfied with their jobs.

In Pakistan, the study by Sahito and Vaisanen (2017) revealed that factors of job satisfaction were found to be salary, career prospects, supervision, management, working environment, and culture. The study further

proved and accepted that highly motivated staff were satisfied and performed their jobs better than poorly motivated staff. This is an expression that there is a significant existence of relationship between teachers' motivational factors and job satisfaction.

On the other hand, a study done by Dağlı and Baysal (2017) on employees' life satisfaction in Turkey affirmed that it is true that people have to make money to meet their physiological and security needs but monetary factors are not effective in motivating teachers. They mentioned recognition, promotion, and opportunity for career growth as the key non-monetary motivating factors for employees.

In Africa also many researchers have investigated the employee's motivation and job performance. For instance, Dina and Olowosoke (2018) examined the effect of motivation and job performance on library personnel effectiveness in university libraries in Nigeria. The study indicated that when effective rewards and recognition are implemented within an organization, a favorable working environment is produced which motivates employees to excel in their performance. Employees take recognition as their feelings of value and appreciation and as a result, it boosts up morale of employees which ultimately increases the productivity of organizations. Rewards play a vital role in determining the significant performance in a job and it is positively associated with the process of motivation.

Maseya and Lusaka (2019) assessed the effect of employee rewards on the performance of employees in Zambia. The study indicated that motivational factors such as rewards, regulation, and economic incentives are perhaps the most important devices that managers can use in the public sector service to retain employees. The study further indicated that nonmonetary incentives such as recognition and training were vital in the organization's performance of the employees.

In a study done in Kenya by Gachengo and Wekesa (2017) on the influence of motivation on employee performance: a case of the National

Bank of Kenya indicated that cash bonus does not affect employee performance. This is because those who received cash bonuses and those who did not all agree that the cash bonus affects their performance the same. The study further suggested that the organization should focus on changing the intrinsic nature and content of jobs. This will increase employee motivation as employees' confidence will get more autonomy and more challenging job assignments and responsibilities.

Another study was conducted in Uganda by Niwamanya (2016) on the effect of financial and non-financial motivation on the performance of teachers in private secondary schools. The findings of their study confirmed that through the use of non-financial motivation, teachers tend to stay longer in their workplaces since they feel that they are valued. Therefore, works of literature prove the significance of non-monetary motivation on employee performance.

In Tanzania, Mpembeni, Bhatnagar, LeFevre, Chitama, Urassa, Kilewo, Mdee, Semu, Winch, Killewo, and Baqui, *et al.*, (2015) conducted a study on motivation and satisfaction among community health workers in Morogoro Region and found that a combination of financial and non-financial incentives is required to support motivation and satisfaction among CHWs but the non-financial are more powerful than the financial ones.

Similarly, Kalangulla (2015) conducted a study on the impact of the reward system on employee performance: A case study of the Bank of Tanzania where the findings indicated that it is obvious those financial rewards positively affect job performance. Similarly, non-financial rewards have the same impact on job performance at BOT. Thus, managers of the bank must pay attention to the way they reward their employees to boost job performance, but it is often time that non-financial rewards are ignored by managers in many organizations.

Furthermore, a study by Buberwa (2015) on academic staff motivation in Tanzania's public higher learning institutions revealed that low monthly salaries were the major factor that dissatisfied academic staff and reduced

motivation for high performance at the University. This study therefore specifically examined the effectiveness of non-monetary motivations on job performance in Tanzania: a case of institutions in Tabora Municipality.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Alderfer (1989) ERG Theory

The theory was developed between 1961 and 1978, during which the theorist empirically tested data to hone the theory's major tenets and published scholarly material. Shin and Kim (2019) argue that ERG is a motivational construct concerned with understanding the factors that contribute to individual human behavior. ERG theory groups human needs into three broad categories: Existence, Relatedness, and Growth (ERG). Existence needs to combine the physiological and safety needs of Maslow's model such as the need for food, shelter, and safe working conditions.

According to Bintang and Musa (2018), the existing needs are satisfied by material incentives. These needs include the basic survival needs of human beings and, the need for physical and psychological safety from threats to people's existence and well-being. Relatedness needs include social and esteem needs, which are derived from other people.

According to Sarkar (2016), relatedness needs to include relationships with other people, receiving public recognition, and feeling secure around people. These needs are satisfied by personal relationships and social interactions.

Growth needs consist of a person's self-esteem through personal achievement as well as the concept of self-actualization. These needs are similar to Maslow's self-actualization needs. This need involves people making creative efforts to achieve their full potential in the existing environment (Bintang and Musa, 2018). These needs will be satisfied only if an individual involves himself in the activities of the organization and searches for new challenges and opportunities. ERG theory offers a more

flexible approach to understanding nonmonetary motivation among employees. Therefore, the theory helps in understanding the effectiveness of non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipality.

Non-Monetary Motivations

All organizations, regardless of sector, size, or industry require a motivated workforce that ensures the efficiency, high organizational output, and prosperity of the organization. Demotivated employees are likely to put in little or no effort in their jobs, produce low-quality work, mostly avoid their workplace, and even exit the organization if provided the opportunity. On the other hand, employees who are motivated to work are likely to be determined, innovative, and competent (Mustafa and Ali, 2019).

As cited in Mani and Mishra (2020), Maslow's theory (1987) showed that one of the most significant factors, that can motivate people in the workplace, was freedom. Management of organizations can give flexibility and freedom in the workplace to improve job performance.

Empirical Literature Review

Recognition and Employees' Job Performance

Recognition plays a vital role in ensuring that employees perform well. Oyagi and Tirimba (2015) in their study indicated that recognition was found to correlate strongly with productivity in a positive manner. The study established that recognition is important for the motivation of employees. It was proposed that employees should be equally recognized as per their output and that the current nature of recognition was inappropriate since the current nature of jobs had not allowed them to be recognized.

A study by Njanja, Maina, Kibet, and Njagi (2013) indicated that reward management is one of the strategies used by Human Resource Managers for attracting and retaining suitable employees as well as facilitating them to improve their performance through motivation and to comply with employment legislation and regulation. As a result of these pressures, HR managers seek to design reward structures that facilitate the organization's strategic goals and

the goals of individual employees. Reward systems are very crucial for an organization.

Similarly, a study by Uzonna (2013) on the impact of motivation on employees' performance in Credit West Bank Cyprus indicated that perhaps one of the most effective ways of motivating a team is to ensure that they understand and appreciate the aims of an organization and are supported by their managers in working towards the achievement of those aims. There are a range of motivational techniques that can be used to improve productivity, reduce workplace stress, and increase self-confidence.

A well-rewarded employee feels that he/she is being valued by the company that he/she is working for. They are also encouraged to work harder and better if they are aware that their well-being is taken seriously by their employers, and that their career and self-development are also being honed and taken care of by their company. Employees are the engine of organization vehicles while the reward is the fuel. No organization can achieve its stated objectives without its employees (Shawa & Sergueeva, 2019).

Promotion and Job Performance

Promotion affects in different styles taking ladders as a motivator but sometimes as a prize and sometimes as an incentive and recruitment. Dina and Olowosoke (2018) examined the effect of motivation and job performance on library personnel effectiveness in university libraries in Nigeria, the result indicated that more talented workers are usually high productivity its assigns according to their skills quickly move toward talented workers. There are some other purposes of the promotion it can help as rewards as past employee effort, promote investment improve productivity, reduce workplace stress, and increase self-confidence.

In their study on the unique motivational factors affecting teacher performance among senior high schools in Kumasi Metropolis by Danquah, Asiamah, and Twumasi (2019) indicated that the major cause of low performance of teachers at the senior high schools was as a result of low

motivation. The study further reported that pay levels and structure are relatively fixed and it is difficult for the head of schools to use the compensation system as a tool to motivate teachers. Promotion is, therefore, the most valuable reward that the head of schools can use as a motivational factor for teachers.

Onanda (2015) studied the effects of motivation on job performance in a case study of the KCB Coast Region. The study revealed that reward had been seen to be a vital instrument in employee performance. A well-rewarded employee feels that he/she is being valued by the company that he/she is working for. They are also encouraged to work harder and better if they are aware that their well-being is taken seriously by their employers, and that their career and self-development are also being honed and taken care of by their company. Employees are the engine of organization vehicles while reward is the fuel. No organization can achieve its stated objectives without its employees.

On the same note, Kunchala, (2017) argues that more talented workers usually have high productivity its assigns according to their skills quickly move toward talented workers. There are some other purposes of the promotion it can help as rewards as past employee effort, promote investment in some specific manner in human capital, and low turnover. There are pre-post and post-promotion jobs for the firm taking as profit from promotion. In the origination, a worker is promoted because they think their status is increased as well as wage rate especially increase later on.

Furthermore, Bintang and Musa (2018) conducted a study on the role of incentives, work satisfaction, and employment motivation with implications on the performance of marketing employees at Bank Dki indicated that different organizations or institutions use promotion as a reward for high productivity of their workers which accelerate their efforts. It can be only a useful way of compensation where an employee gives significant value to promotion, if not then pay or wage increment is the best reward for more exertion. The study

however indicated that promotion can be the best reward when used properly.

Training and Job Performance

Training is a very important tool for the organization to improve the performance of all the personnel for organizational growth and success. The effect of training on employee and organizational performance may be both direct and indirect. According to the study by Sittenthaler and Mohnen (2020), training is important and an imperative tool for the organization to revamp the performance of all the personnel for organizational growth and success. It is beneficial to both employers and employees of an organization. An employee will become more efficient and productive if he is trained well. Firms can develop and enhance the quality of the current employees by providing comprehensive training and development. Training is essential not only to increase productivity but also to motivate and inspire workers by letting them know how important their jobs are and giving them all the information, they need to perform those jobs.

Sittenthaler and Mohnen (2020) on the other hand stipulated the following significance of training for employees as follows;

1. High morale – employees who receive training have increased confidence and motivations
2. Lower cost of production – training eliminates risks because trained personnel can make better and economic use of material and equipment thereby reducing and avoiding waste
3. Lower turnover – training brings a sense of security at the workplace which in turn reduces labor turnover and absenteeism is avoided

Change management – training helps to manage change by increasing the understanding and involvement of employees in the change process and also provides the skills and abilities Firms can develop and enhance the quality of the current employees by providing comprehensive training and development. Training is essential not only to increase productivity but also to

motivate and inspire workers by letting them know how important their jobs are and giving them all the information, they need to perform those jobs.

A study by Muganyizi (2018) postulates that employees' competencies have to be improved through effective training programs. Employee training does not only improve the overall performance of an employee in their current jobs but also increases employees' attitudes, skills, and knowledge for their future job, thus contributing to superior organizational performance. The branch of earlier research on training and employee performance has discovered interesting findings regarding this relationship. Training has been proven to generate performance improvement-related benefits for the employee as well as for the organization by positively influencing employee performance through the development of employee knowledge, skills, ability, competencies, and behavior

Jyothi (2016) studied the non-monetary benefits & their effectiveness in motivating employees as training helps in the individuals' development and growth as well as creating positive attitudes and behaviors in them. Organizations instill in their employees the attitudes and behavior expected from them which in the long run boost the company's image.

Srna and Dinc (2017) examined the significance of non-monetary incentives and their relationship with employee motivation: A case of civil service employees in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The study indicated that training influences employee performance and engagement in several ways. It has shown that training enhances employee performance and engagement in change processes which in turn influences positively employee and organizational performance. The study showed that as a measure of engaging in a change process, the top-level management and non-management management staff are more likely to be induced to take on new tasks compared to those in the middle-level management after undergoing training. Similarly training most

likely motivates the top level to be committed to taking initiative in helping other employees.

Sureephong, Dahlan, Chernbumroong, and Tongpaeng, *et al.* (2020) in their study on the effect of non-monetary rewards on employee performance found that training helps to create good results in performance if training is good performance is also good. Due to training skills and development is properly performed. If the job is performed not well employees are not motivated and in the end, results can't generate up to the mark. Employee participation in questions categorized in major dimensions including decision making improves effectiveness and innovation, enhances employee motivation, and insight into the motivation of employees. The lack of career development affects motivation and performance.

Study Gap

The above-mentioned literature provided strong grounds for understanding the relationship between motivation and employee performance. It is very much evident from the literature that monetary and non-monetary rewards positively influence employee performance. International studies have indicated the existence of a relationship between nonmonetary motivation and job performance. While the reviewed studies in Tanzania predominantly relied on monetary motivational factors on employee's job performance. This reveals a gap and shows the need for examining the effectiveness of non-monetary motivation on job performance. Therefore, the current study examined the effectiveness of non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipality.

Research Methodology

This section aims to discuss the research methodology employed in the research by describing how the study was conducted. The section contains research design, data collection methods, population and sampling procedures, data analysis, presentation and interpretation plan, reliability and validity of data, and ethics considerations.

Study Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design. According to Abutabenjeh and Jarada (2018), descriptive-correlational research design is a framework for planning the study. Creating a research design means making decisions about the type of data needed, respondents, methods of data collection, methods of data analysis, and interpretation. A descriptive correlational research design was used in this study as it helped to evaluate the results and draw conclusions. The design is suitable for this study because it reports things the way they are from the field by describing statistical measures of respondents' perceptions. Similarly, the design was used to evaluate and explain the statistical measures of the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

On the other hand, the study employed a quantitative research approach. According to Bloomfield and Fisher (2019), quantitative methods involve the processes of collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and writing the results of a study using various designs including the descriptive-correlational research design. A quantitative approach was used in this study by finding frequencies, means, standard deviations, and correlations to examine the relationships among variables of non-monetary motivation and job performance. As the numerical data that were collected can be analyzed using specific statistical procedures, the approach was suitable for this study. Since the perspectives of the dependent variable in its four measures (specific assigned tasks per time, level of employee commitment, level of productivity returns, and employer's expectations) and the independent variable in its three measures (recognition, promotion, and training) are assessed quantitatively again the mentioned approach were suitable in this study.

Data Collection Methods

The researcher used questionnaires to collect information from employees from Tabora Municipality. The questionnaires used were close-ended questionnaires to collect data from respondents. According to Paradis, O'Brien,

Nimmon, Bandiera, and Martimianakis, et al., (2016), questionnaires are effective in data collection because they are practical and cover a large number of respondents compared to other methods. The advantage of questionnaires is that the information generated can be verified and cross-checked against other data collection techniques.

Kumar, (2014) defined a questionnaire as a research instrument consisting of a series of questions to gather information from respondents. The questionnaires were distributed to departments in TMC in general. The reason to apply questionnaires for data collection is because; the method makes respondents free to air their views to enable the researcher to get more information from respondents. The questions in the questionnaires are semi-structured. A semi-structured questionnaire is a mix of unstructured and structured questionnaires. Some of the questions and their sequence are determined in advance; hence questionnaire contained both open-ended and closed-ended questions

Before distributing questionnaires a pilot study was conducted to pre-test respondents to ensure that there were no ambiguous or unnecessary questions and to make the instrument able to draw the responses required to achieve the research objectives. The process of clearing doubts in the pre-test stage ensures that the content of the questionnaire is relevant, adequate, clear in wording, and suited to the understanding of the respondents just like (Kumar, 2014). This also lays the ground for developing appropriate procedures for administering the questionnaire with orientation to the situation of the field.

Questionnaires had five options for respondents to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement as follows: 1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral 4=Agree and 5 = Strongly Agree.

Population and Sampling Procedures

Population

In this study, the targeted population is the employees and members of management from

Tabora Municipality, which is one of the public organizations under local governments' authority in Tanzania. According to the Ministry of Regional Administration and Local Governments Tabora Municipal Council is one of the local government authorities that have used effectively both non-monetary and monetary motivations in evaluating workers' performance for five consecutive years (MRALG 2020).

Public organizations in Tanzania exhibit coherent procedures in administering their activities including that of motivating human resources and evaluating job performance. The selection of this entity is to enable the researcher to have an in-depth understanding of the effectiveness of non-monetary motivations on job performance. The total population of employees in Tabora Municipality is 200 with 21 members of management (Tabora Municipality, 2021). The population of the study refers to the comprehensive group of individuals, institutions, and objects with a common characteristic that is the interest of a researcher. A well-chosen population contains most of the information about a particular population parameter but the relation between the sample

and the population must be such as to allow true inferences to be made about a population from that sample as referred by (Akthar, 2016; and Alvi, 2016).

Sample Size

According to Friedman, Furberg, DeMets, Reboussin, and Granger *et al*, (2015), sampling is a process used in statistical analysis in which a predetermined number of observations are taken from a larger population. The methodology used to sample from a larger population depends on the type of analysis being performed. In this study, the sample was obtained using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table of determining sample size (see Appendix II attached). According to this table, when the population is 200, the sample size will be 133. Therefore, the sample size for this study constituted 133 employees of TMC. On the side of members of management, since the population of 21 members is small then all 21 members were included in a sample. There are 13 heads and assistant heads of departments, 1 human resource director, and 1 human resource officer who constitute 15 members of the management of TMC and are relevant to evaluate the workers' job performance at TMC.

Table 1. Distribution of Employees, Heads, and Assistant Heads of Staff in Tabora Municipal Council

TABORA MUNICIPAL COUNCIL				
	TARGETED DEPARTMENT	Management	Employees	Sample size
1	Groundworkers	2	45	30
2	Accounts Department	2	23	15
3	Administrative Department	4	94	62
4	Procurement and Logistics Department	3	15	10
5	IT Department	2	23	15
6	Human Resources	2	-	-
	TOTAL	15	200	133

Source: Tabora Municipal Council, 2021-Field data

The sample size of the study will comprise 133 employees and 15 members of management of Tabora Municipality from the five departments. For employees, the sample size of the study was determined by using Taro Yamane's mathematical formula as calculated below, while

the sample size from each organization was determined by the Survey Monkey tool.

The five (5) departments of Tabora Municipality have a total of 200 staff working, 133 staff were selected to respond to the questionnaires. The 133 sampled staff account for 66.5% of the staff

population working in Tabora Municipality. The 133 respondents were selected from employees whose working experience at the municipality is not less than three years as these respondents can give reliable information on the experience of non-monetary motivations (Kumar, 2014).

Sampling Techniques

Kumar (2014) argues that the sampling technique is a procedure that the researcher would adopt to select items for the sample. It is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population since it is difficult to study a whole population (Ibid). Furthermore, Kumar (2014) emphasized that there are two major goals that sampling techniques intend to achieve.

The first is to establish representatives of what is being studied and conversely to reduce bias. The second is to be able to make inferences from findings based on a sample to a larger population from which that sample was drawn. In this study, the researcher employed stratified and purposive sampling techniques to get the required subjects for the sample from the population.

In using the stratified random sampling techniques Etikan and Bala (2017), argue that stratified sampling is a probability sampling technique where the researcher divides the entire population into different subgroups or strata, and then randomly selects the final subjects proportionally from the various strata. The researcher used the proportional allocation technique where the sample size in a department was made proportional to the number of populations present in the entire department. This sampling method gives an equal chance for all employees to be involved in the study.

Furthermore, stratified sampling can be combined with purposive sampling techniques. According to Tkachenko, Hahn, & Peterson, (2017), stratified and purposive sampling involves dividing the population into homogeneous subgroups and then purposely selecting a sample from each subgroup to use in the study. Kumar (2014) defined purposive sampling as a set of procedures where the researcher manipulates the analysis, approach, and sampling activity interactively during the

research process to a much greater extent than in statistical sampling. Furthermore, Kumar (2014) defined purposive sampling as a deliberate selection of particular departments of the population to constitute a sample that represents the population. The use of stratified and purposive sampling generally has more arithmetical accuracy in the data than purposive sampling alone (Tkachenko, Hahn, & Peterson, 2017).

In this case, employees were grouped into strata according to their departments and then the selection of the study sample was purposively made disproportionately. This means stratified sampling and purposive sampling were used in this study to sample employees from their departments of the organization with the condition that each selected employee must have at least three years of working experience in Tabora Municipal Council. The use of a purposeful sampling technique is aimed at enabling the selection of respondents who can generate vital information regarding the effectiveness of non-monetary motivations on employee job performance. Also, the use of this procedure is to be able to represent not only the overall population but also to represent those departments with fewer employees.

For members of management, the sampling procedure used is total population sampling which falls under the non-probability sampling technique. The sampling procedure is applied since there are few members of the population to be included in a sample thus all 15 staff who participate in management are included.

Data Analysis, Presentation, and Interpretation Plan

According to Mellinger and Hanson (2016), data analysis is the process of inspecting, rearranging, modifying, and transforming data to extract useful information from it. Also, it is important to make sure that data analysis is done responsibly for determining the patterns of the relationships among the variables relating to it. Since the study collected numerical data, the suitable method of analysis for objective one and two were descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) with the aid of SPSS Version

22. Pearson's Correlation was used to establish the relationship between non-monetary motivation and job performance in Tabora Municipality. Interpretation of findings was done using the four-point Likert scale. Presentation of findings was done using tables, and figures.

Validity and Reliability

This was achieved by setting standards for constructing questionnaires and interview questions related to the research objectives and questions. Interviews and questionnaires were produced in conjunction with the researcher making sure that the questionnaire and interviews concentrate on the topic under the study. During the pre-data collection period before the distribution of the main questionnaires, the reasons for the study were openly explained to the respondents, and matters concerns were resolved satisfactorily. The procedures of the interviews and questionnaires were explained to the respondents. Respondents were guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality.

Table 2. Reliability Analysis Results

SN	Variable in Question	Cronibach's Alpha	Status
1	Recognition	0.869	Reliable
2	Promotion	0.844	Reliable
3	Training	0.843	Reliable

According to the results in Table 2 Cronibach's Alpha for Recognition is 0.869, for Promotion is 0.844 and for Training is 0.843. Therefore, it was concluded that the questionnaire for data collection was reliable.

This was achieved by setting standards for constructing questionnaire questions related to the research objectives and questions. Questionnaires were produced in conjunction with the researcher making sure that the questionnaire concentrates on the topic under the study. During the pre-data collection period before the distribution of the main questionnaires, the reasons for the study were openly explained to the respondents, and

matters concerns were resolved satisfactorily. The procedures of the questionnaires were explained to the respondents. Respondents were guaranteed anonymity and confidentiality.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher solicited information voluntarily and kept all the data and information available from respondents and those extracted from the documentary review confidential. Furthermore, all the respondents were respected and the information given was protected from those persons who are thought to be unwanted to prevent harm or threats that may be directed to the respondent due to the information given.

Data Analysis, Presentation, and Interpretation plan

In this study, the researcher used quantitative data analysis and the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23 which is computer program software to analyze data of respondents from questionnaires of the closed-ended questions which were edited, coded, and entered in the SPSS software.

SPSS is a large and powerful general-purpose statistical package with excellent data management facilities and high-quality graphics (Kumar, 2014). It was often depicted as one of the friendliest statistical packages of its type, with a good graphical user interface and plenty of built-in documentation.

Once the data editing and data coding were done and quantified, the researcher entered data into the SPSS program software. Hence, the SPSS assisted the researcher in extracting descriptive statistics such as frequencies. Data were organized into frequency tables from which the means, and percentages will be calculated. Therefore, descriptive statistical techniques will be used to obtain frequencies, analyze and summarize data before making inferences through Hypothesis testing by analyzing relationships between variables and make population comparisons through the use of sample data. This study had four specific research objectives given as follows:

- 1) To examine the process of Recognizing workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipality
- 2) To examine the process of Promoting workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipality
- 3) To determine the process of Training workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipality
- 4) To determine the relationship between non-monetary motivations and employees' job performance in Tabora Municipality

Descriptive Analysis of Data

According to data analysis, demographic analysis observed the following results: Sex wise-male respondents were 82 which is 55.4%, and females were 66 which is 44.6%. Age shows that the majority of the respondents whose age group falls in 30-39 are 56 respondents equivalent to

37.84 percent, followed by the 20-29 age group comprised of 41 respondents equivalent to 27.70 percent. Findings also show that the majority of the respondents had a bachelor's degree level of education who are 68 (45.9%), followed by diploma holders 53 (35.8%).

Results also show that the majority of the employee respondents were those in the Administrative department 94(70.68%). Furthermore, results show that the majority of the respondents had between 6-10 years of working experience who are 53 (36%), the period between 11 and 15 years 42 (28%). These findings are similar to those of (Kipleting 2017). Mpembeni et al., (2015) in their study about the influence of non-monetary motivations on employees' job performance in Tanzania found that the higher proportion number of workers in an organization works in the experience group of 6 to 10 years.

Table 3. Perception of respondents on non-monetary motivation practices

SN	Questionnaire Item	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation
1	The institution practices recognition	125	84	Agreed
2	The institution practices the promotion of awards	132	89.2	Agreed
3	The institution practices training awards	127	85.8	Agreed

Perception of employees and management members on institution practices of recognition awards at least every year indicates that 125 respondents, about 84 percent believed that they have seen recognition practiced as non-monetary motivation to workers. Perception of the institution's practices on promotion awards to employees at least every year indicates that 132 respondents, about 89.2 percent believed that they have seen promotions practiced as non-monetary motivation to workers. Perception of the institution's practices on training awards to employees at least every year indicates that 127 respondents, about 85.8 percent thought that they have seen training practiced as non-monetary motivation to workers.

The above findings corroborate with those of Emerole (2017) in the study about the effectiveness of non-monetary motivations in

Nigeria whereby he found that a higher proportion number of workers in public institutions are motivated to work by training, promotions, and recognition practices.

Research Objective 1. To examine the process of Recognizing workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipality

Perception of employees and management members on the institution's use of formal processes in practices of recognition awards indicates that 88 respondents, about 59.5 percent believed that they have seen the use of formal procedures in recognition practiced as non-monetary motivation to workers, based on labor and employment policy 112 (75.7%), use evaluation feedback reports to grant awards 98 (66.2%) of all respondents working in Tabora Municipality.

Research Objective 2. To examine the process of Promoting workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipality

Perception of employees and management members on the institution's use of formal processes in practices of promotion awards indicates that 78 respondents, about 52.7 percent believed that they have seen the use of formal procedures in promotion practiced as non-monetary motivation to workers, based on labor and employment policy 118 (79.7%), use evaluation feedback reports to grant awards 84 (56.8%) of all selected respondents working in Tabora Municipality.

Research Objective 3. To determine the process of Training workers as non-monetary motivation on job performance in Tabora Municipality

Perception of employees and management members on the institution's use of formal processes in practices of training awards indicates that 97 respondents, about 65.5 percent thought that they have seen the use of formal procedures in training practiced as non-

monetary motivation to workers, based on labor and employment policy 105 (70.9%), use evaluation feedback reports to grant awards 83 (56.1) of all selected respondents working in Tabora Municipality. Specifically, the practices of non-monetary motivations have enabled employees to understand how to link the institution's policy instruments with their day-to-day activities in the institution.

Research Objective 4. To determine the relationship between non-monetary motivations and employees' job performance in Tabora Municipality

One of the major aims of non-monetary motivation is to improve work performance and has to be used both by management and workers. This question aimed at knowing if all the practice of non-monetary motivations has enhanced the work performance of employees in their institution.

H0: There is no statistically significant relationship between the non-monetary motivations and job performance at Tabora Municipality.

Table 4. Correlations between Variables

		Recognition	Promotion	Training	Targets per time	Commitment to job	Productivity	Expectations
Recognition	Pearson Correlation	1	.168*	.095	.499**	.781**	.656**	.563**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.039	.245	.009	.000	.008	.002
	N	148	148	148	148	148	148	148
Promotion	Pearson Correlation	.168*	1	.309*	.639*	.819**	.319*	.689**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.039		.043	.000	.000	.052	.000
	N	148	148	148	146	147	145	148
Training	Pearson Correlation	.095	.109*	1	.513**	-.229*	.729**	.317
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.245	.041		.000	.026	.000	.046
	N	147	148	148	148	147	148	148
Targets per time	Pearson Correlation	.057	.516**	.592**	.535**	-.033	-.033	-.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.484	.000	.000	.000	.686	.686	.686
	N	148	148	147	148	147	147	148
Commitment to job	Pearson Correlation	.099	.439**	.413**	1	.227**	.227**	.227**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.229	.000	.000		.005	.005	.005
	N	148	148	148	148	147	148	148
Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.527**	.166*	.287**	.158	.399**	.399**	.399**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.041	.000	.053	.000	.000	.000
	N	148	147	148	147	147	148	148

Expectations	Pearson Correlation	.781**	-.119	.029	.227**	1	1	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.144	.729	.005			
	N	148	146	148	148	147	148	147

Note: ** Statistically significant at 0.01 and * statistically significant at 0.05

Results from the study showed that non-monetary motivations that as recognition, promotion, and training have a positive and significant effect on employees' job performance, the values of Pearson correlational coefficients for Recognition are 0.499, 0.781, and 0.656 and 0.563 for target achievement per time, increase of commitment to job, raising productivity returns and raising employer's expectations respectively and are statistically significant at P-value 0.01. The Promotion variable reveals a positive and significant effect on employees' job performance; the values of Pearson correlational coefficients for the Promotion variable are 0.639, 0.819, and 0.319 and 0.639 for target achievement per time, increase of commitment to the job, raising productivity returns and raising employer's expectations respectively and are statistically significant at P-value 0.01. Results from the study further showed that Training has a positive effect on commitment to the job, and have significant effect on employees' job performance; the values of Pearson correlational coefficients for Training are 0.513, -0.229, 0.729, and 0.319 respectively, and statistically significant at P-value 0.01.

Discussion

Although non-monetary motivations are regarded as effective and efficient tools for promoting job performance, they are still on specific standards for managing public sector institutions and are most useful for enhancing ethics and work culture in the institutions. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of non-monetary motivations relies on features such as promoting workers' incentives to achieve set targets per time, job commitment, increased productivity returns, and meeting employer's expectations to evaluate individual employees' performance.

However, the most important advantage of non-monetary motivations at Tabora Municipal Council is that institutional employees gain a better understanding of institutional priorities, general employer desires, and the management's willingness and ability to provide the institutional objectives needed. One of the disadvantages of this approach is that many employees consider this type of incentive and drive to performance as an opportunity to gain positions, and some see it as an opportunity to provide an involuntary commitment to the job. In sum, most respondents have evaluated their relationship to non-monetary motivations practiced based on their institutional strength and actual performance.

Conclusion

The objectives of the study were met and the research questions were answered. From the study, it was concluded that there is a relationship between non-monetary motivations and job performance. Recognition positively triggers the achievement of set targets per time at Tabora Municipal Council. This role has contributed to job performance and alignment of the institution in its implementation of goals.

Recognition, promotion, and training have been instrumental in driving and motivating employees through fairly appreciating the activities accomplished by workers. Recognition, Promotion, and Training have similarly played key roles in driving and motivating employees through fairly appreciating the activities accomplished by workers by shifting best performers to top positions increasing work capacities, morale, and commitment.

Non-monetary motivations are not tools that are not well-known by many employees in public sector institutions. Currently, they are the most

known types of raising productivity, and job commitment and increasing employees' desire to fulfill employers and institution goals.

Recommendations

Management members should be trained properly to conduct the employee performance review as one of the tool requirements in granting non-monetary motivation awards to workers. They also need to understand the importance of conducting employee performance reviews from a long-term perspective. They should be given the motivation to carry out these human resource activities as well as make them aware of the consequences of weak relationships to any employee on job performance. This can be ensured by evaluating their interactions with them and a constant attitude of positive welcome on any issue that can demand clarification in OPRAS.

There should be reasonable compensation for higher employee performers and this compensation should be based on equal, fair, and transparent evaluation. The management member has a role to play in terms of rewarding higher performers but high performance should be proportional to its reward if we are to increase the morale of the employees.

There should be a clear methodology while conducting recruitment for non-monetary motivation to avoid misconception of it. Strategies should be clearly understood as well as the expectation of the outcome for each of the institution's employees.

Theoretical and Contextual Contribution

This study has made an immense contribution to various stakeholders in the field of human resources management. First, the study gap in placing due importance on non-monetary motivations in institutional practices has been identified. This will help future researchers to come up with topics for further investigation. Secondly, awareness has been created in the

government Ministry of Labor, to realize the significance of the role played by non-monetary motivations in job performance. This will enable the ministry to undertake an analysis of factors hindering institutions from effectively fulfilling the responsibility of motivating employees, and this will benefit public institutions through better job performance of employees.

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